

The rise of battery-run rickshaws in Bangladesh: Causes, Effects, Solution, and Benefits

The research is conducted under the Intent Research Center.

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Abstract:

The advent of battery-run rickshaws in Bangladesh has revolutionized mass transport, providing millions of people with affordable transport and livelihood opportunities while creating enormous challenges to mobility and safety. The research debunks the primitive explanations for their spread, e.g., economic necessity, mass unemployment, and absence of regulatory control, and their effects on traffic congestion, road safety, and exclusion of traditional rickshaw pullers. Based on qualitative inputs from 23 secondary sources in the form of news articles and research papers spanning 12 years, with recent trends being the emphasis, the study brings to light the socio-economic gains and infrastructural cost exacted by the battery-operated rickshaw. It recommends a blend of short-term measures, i.e., improved licensing, safety standards, as well as long-term strategies like exclusive route optimization, and green charging infrastructure. The study validates an overarching, equitable regulatory policy to optimize the potential of battery-run rickshaws, especially their accessibility for persons with disability, while referring to their adverse effects on infrastructure and traditional rickshaw livelihood.

Keywords

Battery-run rickshaw, affordable transportation, mass employment, traffic Congestion, safety standards, green charging infrastructure

1. Introduction:

Rickshaw represents the colorful heritage of our country. The word "rickshaw" originated in Japan during the late 19th to early 20th century. Afterward, millions of these vehicles were produced in mass numbers and distributed all over the South Asian region. The origin of rickshaws in Dhaka city can be traced back to Kolkata around 1930, when a wealthy merchant introduced them. And afterward, rickshaws gradually became one of the most popular ways of transportation (*Rickshaw - Banglapedia*, n.d.). But the journey in the battery-run rickshaw was very new. During 2007, some rickshaw owners modified their paddle rickshaws by installing electric motors and acid car batteries to make their rickshaws faster (Rabbi, 2024). And very soon, battery-run rickshaws started to gain popularity, primarily due to being cheaper and faster compared to an ordinary paddle-run rickshaw. As a result, battery-run rickshaws started to become obsolete compared to paddle-run rickshaws, and this trend has been observed all over the country. In recent times, battery-run rickshaws are now in a state of replacing traditional paddle rickshaws. And

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there are different hypotheses for this phenomenon. For example, many battery-run rickshaw drivers have suggested that their battery-run rickshaws are more comfortable to ride, and they can use their rickshaw for long hours at a time, which gives them a higher return on profit; they can easily manufacture their rickshaw, and the lower maintenance gives them an extra edge. In the legal framework, they get tax exemption on rickshaw components like electric motors, batteries, and the availability of illegal electric charging stations are some of the hypothetical reasons behind the rise of battery-run rickshaws in Bangladesh in recent times.

Expansion of battery-run rickshaws is supposed to have a positive impact in terms of both economic and environmental factors. However, in reality, they have now become one of the most significant hazards on the roads of Bangladesh. If we look at some statistics, we see that in 2016, the total registered number of battery-run rickshaws was around 200,000, but in 2024, this number is estimated to be around 4 to 6 million (Earth, 2025). Another data source says that the total number of registered paddle rickshaws is around 1.2 to 1.3 million (Karim & Salam, 2019). On the other hand, the total percentage of usable roads and highways is less than 7 to 9 percent compared to an ideal case, which was supposed to be more than 25 percent (Noor, R. E., Imran, M., & Hossain, M. I., 2016). If we put that data side by side, we can clearly say that we have very limited usable roads. However, the number of battery-run rickshaws is rising at a staggering rate. As a result, traffic-congested roads, rising traffic accidents, and many other problems have risen quite significantly in recent times. And the objective of our research is to find out.

2. Methodology:

For this research, we have used a qualitative research approach where the research data is collected from secondary sources such as news articles and research papers. We have analyzed around 25 research papers and news articles from a time frame of 12 years, and the recent 5 years of data were mainly used to analyze the actual reason for our research problem. The dynamic approach of both time series and the variety of data sources will give us a dynamic understanding of our research topic, help us to understand the possible causes and effects, and identify potential solutions.

3. Cause of the problem:

One of the primary questions this research aims to answer is why the number of battery-run rickshaws in Bangladesh has increased. To answer this question, we considered different factors such as economic conditions, unemployment, low tariff of spare parts, changing vehicle preferences, lower investment, higher ROI, minimum operating costs in this business, and so on. We have discussed the causes in three broader aspects.

3.1 Unemployment and higher income:

One of the primary reasons for the rise of battery-run rickshaws was seasonal and full-time unemployment. Research conducted by the University of Chittagong in 151 battery-run rickshaws in 10 selected study areas at Chittagong city, which shows a result where around 49% percent of the battery run rickshaw driver choose this profession from their consent, and the research also suggests that battery run rickshaw driver are earning two times more compared to their previous occupation (Mazumder & Roy, 2018). Through this data, we get a very different perspective regarding the case of our problem, and it is evident that more and more unemployed people are willing to have this vehicle as the source of their income and livelihood.

3.2 Low import duty and unregulated speed limit of motors:

The availability of spare parts and lower import duty make this vehicle even more lucrative to operate. Data shows that before the fiscal year 2025-2026, the customs duty on a 1200-watt motor was only 1%, which was recently increased by 15 to 20 percent under the supervision of the current interim government (Dhaka Tribune,2025). One of the primary parts of the battery-run rickshaw is its axle motor. While opening the LC, most of the importers do not mention the speed limit or any specifications regarding those imports, which creates safety hazards in the future.

3.3 Low investment, Higher ROI:

Most battery-run rickshaws are not owned by their drivers but rather by the local garage owner. Drivers operate those vehicles on a daily rental basis, as it has high demand among the unemployed population. Considering the advantage of the increased influx of unemployed population in the cities and towns, garage owners are making a fortune through investing in battery-run rickshaws. As the battery-run rickshaw is a comparatively less capital-intensive venture, garage owners see battery rickshaws as a source of easy money since manufacturing and maintaining them is very cheap. Besides, garage owners use the illegal electricity lines to charge batteries, and the operating costs go much lower. While drivers get a minimum share of earnings, most of the income goes to the garage owners. So, the return on investment is very high in this business compared to others.

4. Effects of uncontrolled battery-run rickshaws:

Besides that, if we analyze the effects, we can identify some primary effects that result in the rise of battery-run rickshaws.

4.1 Decrease in average fare price:

First of all, the average fare price significantly reduced compared to its paddle-run rickshaw counterpart. This phenomenon happens due to the basic economic principle of supply and demand. To support this argument, one research study has been conducted, which says on average, battery-run rickshaws pay 2 to 5 TK less compared to pedal rickshaws (Islam, 2013). As a result, this creates an intense competition, especially from pedal-run rickshaws.

4.2 Increased electricity consumption:

A survey conducted in Rangpur city shows that in 2012, there were only 400 battery-run rickshaws, and another recent survey conducted in 2019 shows there are a total of 6500 battery-run rickshaws, which shows that the battery-run rickshaws have increased by 16.25 times in Rangpur city. The majority of the paddle-run rickshaws have been replaced by this battery-run rickshaw (Rahman et al., 2019). Even though battery-run rickshaws charge a lower fare, the larger volume of trips they can take compared to the paddle-run rickshaw still makes them much more profitable compared to a paddle-run rickshaw.

Battery-run rickshaws need electricity to recharge. The consumption of electricity has increased exponentially to recharge the batteries. As most of the garage owners are using illegal electricity connections, the state-owned power distribution company is losing a big chunk of revenue. But they are to pay the electricity producing companies, despite incurring substantial financial losses. Ultimately, this financial burden is being transferred to the industrial, commercial, and residential users in the form of a higher tariff to reduce system loss. And again, due to higher utility expenses, the price of goods and services increases, which ultimately general consumers are paying. So, battery-run rickshaw also plays a key role in increased utility costs.

Paddel riskshaw and Battery run rickshaw

4.3 Increase in traffic jams and road accidents:

On the other hand, the high number of battery-run rickshaws in an urban space can create massive traffic congestion. A news article from Sylhet says that on an average day, around 5000 auto rickshaws flood the streets of Sreemangal and ultimately paralyze the city (Dhaka Tribune, 2024). A battery-run rickshaw creates safety hazards on the road since they are heavily modified with poor-quality equipment and run much faster than a conventional paddle rickshaw, which also lacks any kind of safety feature for the passenger. As a result, battery-run rickshaws encounter a higher rate of accidents on the road. Data from a news article says that around 870 accidents have taken place in 2024, which caused 875 deaths and 1,779 injuries, making battery-run rickshaws one of the top contributors to road casualties in Bangladesh. (Dhaka Tribune, 2025; The Financial Express, 2025).

5. Proposed solution and action plan:

To find a solution for this growing problem, a proper plan of action needs to be put into action. We recommend dividing plans of action into both long-term and short-term. Short-term plans are those plans that can be taken action immediately, which will be very effective in the short run. On the other hand, while the short-run plans were being executed to control the exploding number of battery-run rickshaws on the road immediately, some sustainable long-term action plans will slowly take place to overcome this problem.

5.1 Short-term action plans:

The proposed short-term plans will consist of substantial involvement of law enforcement, which will include shutting down all illegal manufacturing plants, closing illegal charging stations at garages, and a strict licensing policy to ban all three-wheelers on highways. And we also recommend changing this import policy by increasing the tariff for motor and other spare parts, and ensuring that each vital component will go through under strict regulation, and importers must mention the speed limit while opening an LC. And if those short-term policies took place, we could expect to see an immediate result after a short time.

5.2 Long-term action plans:

On the other hand, the proposed long-term action will primarily focus on sustainable infrastructure development and some institutions that will monitor the overall process. The established institution will implement strict codes for manufacturing and modifying vehicles, which the experts in this field will set. And the government will work as a monetization agency for this overall process. A news report shows that the total battery-run rickshaw industry is worth 9.7 billion dollars (CLEAN, 2024), which creates a huge business opportunity for entrepreneurs to enter this market. And if this market becomes more competitive, it is expected that the quality and safety of those vehicles will significantly improve since intense competition is always better for consumers (Zaur Asadzade, 2024).

Besides that, dedicated route mapping needs to be implemented all over the country, starting with pilot projects. As we have previously seen, implementing a large-scale route rationalization project plan in a short time is not so effective. So, we recommend that at first, battery-run rickshaws should be banned permanently on some dedicated highways, and then slowly, they should be expanded to all the highways. Finally, we have to apply the dedicated route rationalization for all the battery-run rickshaws on the road.

5.3 Implementation of some digitized action plans:

We also recommend that some digitized solutions can be implemented between long-term and short-term plans, such as building well-regulated charging stations around the city to charge those vehicles. Digitized number plates include RFID, GPS, or QR code for easy recognition and tracking, which can be installed on the number plate to monitor the overall rickshaw movement and to identify the traffic-congested points in the city. This data would be shared with the traffic police to take immediate action. And we recommend that this overall system, from manufacturing digitized number plates to a GPS tracking system, should be built by private companies, and government institutions should monetize their operations.

6. Benefits of using a battery-run rickshaw:

From a general perspective, battery-run rickshaws on the streets are considered to be a problem. However, from another perspective, they have some significant positive aspects. They have a vast potential to solve the public transportation problem in Bangladesh.

6.1 Environmentally friendly:

To start with, a battery-run rickshaw is very eco-friendly and sustainable. They have higher productivity compared to a paddle-run rickshaw, and they can carry more passengers in a short period, which gives them better efficiency. Uses of modified battery-run solar-powered rickshaws can be used for even more efficiency. Research shows that an auto rickshaw garage, on average, charges 30 rickshaws per day, which consumes 290 kWh, and installing solar panels on the roof of rickshaw hoods can make those rickshaws almost self-sufficient. As a result, it could reduce yearly emissions of 54 tons of CO₂ (Uddin et al., 2021).

6.2 Health-friendly:

Battery-run rickshaws are a healthier option for their drivers as well. One research conducted between the age group of 25 to 60 showed that 62.7% paddle-run rickshaw drivers have lower back pain, and 75.4% had minimal disability (Islam et al., 2020). This data shows how the paddle-run rickshaw is silently creating health hazards in the long run. On the other hand, battery-run rickshaw drivers do not have to pull their rickshaw using a paddle, which is done by an electric motor, and that is why they can carry more passengers while minimizing their health risk.

6.3 Good for people with disabilities:

Besides that, another shocking discovery we have made is that most of the paddle-run rickshaw pullers are becoming disabled at one point in their life. One research study conducted shows that around 94 % of the rickshaw pullers face some sort of health issue, and 34.5% who are above 40 years are not able to continue rickshaw pulling (Sultana, 2024). At one point in life, they become fully disabled. However, in the case of a battery-run rickshaw, this situation is very different since battery-run rickshaw drivers do not face any kind of health risk while driving their rickshaw for long hours at a time for years.

To sum up, we can say that the majority of the problems regarding battery-run rickshaws are all about the overcrowding of the roads, but if we can operate battery-run rickshaws in a controlled manner with a well-regulated structure, it could become a viable alternative option for public transport.

7. Conclusion:

In conclusion, it can be said that the rise of battery-run rickshaws in Bangladesh is a complex reality. On one hand, battery-run rickshaws provide cheap public transportation, as well as creating tremendous job opportunities and eco-friendly transportation measures for the masses. But their unchecked exponential growth has generated many urban issues, such as traffic congestion, road safety hazards, and price discrimination between pedal-run rickshaws and battery-run rickshaws. Our study suggests the actual cause of the uncontrollable growth of battery-run rickshaws, which encompasses a lack of enforcement of traffic regulations, the absence of proper licensing and monitoring, and unemployment. Both the city infrastructure and the passengers are experiencing the consequences, as untrained drivers with unsafe modified rickshaws result in congested roads and unsafe rides for the passengers. Overall, this is ultimately lowering the quality of life in Bangladesh. Yet the problem is not insurmountable.

Numerous solutions and action plans can be undertaken in the short and long term. Steps such as a strict licensing policy, building well-regulated charging stations, import prohibition, monetization on key components, zoning traffic routes, banning rickshaws from operating on major highways, and, to some extent, privatization can discipline the industry. On the other hand, some immediate steps, such as fare regulation, a crackdown on unauthorized modification workshops, supported by long-term private sector investment, sustainable transport planning, and green infrastructure, could be a near-term step for this problem. To guarantee the continued benefits of battery-run rickshaws without sacrificing any safety features or efficiency, our policymakers must act quickly and firmly. An integrated, balanced, and managed approach will not just reduce urban traffic issues but also create a cleaner, safer, and more equitable urban transport system for the future.

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